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The Effect of Green Intellectual Capital on Organizational Reputation

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Abstract: The research reviews the understanding of the impact of green intellectual capital on organizational reputation by analyzing the relationship between their dimensions. It aims to assist the management of private universities and colleges in enhancing sustainable environmental performance. The study began with a main problem that included questions about the nature of the relationship between its variables, including the extent of interest of private universities in Karbala in green intellectual capital and its dimensions. The study adopted purposive sampling, with the number of individuals who responded to the study being 131 leaders and academics. Utilized various statistical methods such as SPSS and AMOS. The results showed significant correlation and influence between green intellectual capital and organizational reputation. The recommend increasing focus on green intellectual capital dimensions to improve organizational reputation.

Keywords: Green Intellectual Capital, Organizational Reputation, Private Universities, Iraq.

Introduction

With the increasing environmental and social challenges in the world, sustainable strategies have become a necessity for the success of institutions in the current era. Green intellectual capital is

considered a vital element that combines innovation and sustainability, as it contributes to building a strong reputation for institutions by developing products and services that reflect improved environmental and social quality, and building a positive organizational image that reflects their commitment to social and environmental responsibility. The importance of this study is evident in exploring the impact of green intellectual capital on the reputation of private universities, and identifying ways that contribute to enhancing their distinction and attractiveness as centers of higher education committed to sustainability and social responsibility. The role of private universities in Karbala as influential centers in improving society is highlighted, as their adoption of green ideas and their response to environmental and economic challenges is enhanced by acting effectively and efficiently. The research also reviews the importance of institutions investing in sustainability and the environment in enhancing their reputation and public confidence in them.

Literature Review

Green Intellectual Capital

The first to introduce green intellectual capital (Chen, 2008:277) defined it as the accumulation of intangible and non-material assets, knowledge, capabilities and employee-level connections related to environmental protection and environmental innovation within the organization. Chahal & Bakshi, 2014:60 added that green intellectual capital represents an intangible resource that has the potential to add value in the future, as it is represented in the use of knowledge and experiences to innovate new ideas and develop environmentally sustainable products. Yusliza et al., 2020:8 explained that green intellectual capital is the complete set of knowledge that enables the organization to benefit from managing environmental issues to achieve competitive advantage. On the other hand, Bombiak, 2023:5 described green intellectual capital as the complete knowledge that the organization possesses and employs in environmental management. According to Arie et al., 2019:227, green intellectual capital is a strategy for developing organizations based on sustainability and environmental friendliness and includes consideration of environmental impact and sustainable benefits. (Gharib et al., 2023:4) explained that green intellectual capital represents the resources and values associated with environmental and social sustainability that contribute to achieving competitive superiority for institutions. (Li et al., 2023:5) defined it as the experiences that organizations possess regarding environmental and social issues. In light of the above, the researchers believe that the concept of green intellectual capital is the comprehensive set of intangible resources that focus on innovation and environmental sustainability in operations, products and services, such as knowledge, green technologies, and innovative environmental designs, as it aims to achieve sustainable development and improve the environmental and social impact of organizations. On the other hand, studies have shown, including the study by (Yong et al., 2019:7), that green intellectual capital plays a vital role in the sustainability and innovation of organizations, as it combines the concepts of intellectual capital and the growing interest in the environment. This shift is very important because it enhances environmental innovation and sustainability, and gives organizations a competitive advantage, as it contributes to enhancing effective environmental management through employee participation in implementing environmental initiatives and increasing environmental awareness within the organization, and achieving the dimensions of green intellectual capital. (Bombiak, 2022:5-

6) added that green intellectual capital plays a vital role in developing organizations, as it enhances environmental, economic and social performance, and contributes to achieving competitive advantages and attracting employees, which enhances sustainable businesses and improves financial and environmental performance. The scale (Chen, 2008:274-275) was chosen, which includes three dimensions: (Green Human Capital, Green Structural Capital, Green Relational Capital). This scale is comprehensive for the dimensions of this study, and is distinguished by including ready-made paragraphs to measure each dimension, as the arbitrators agreed on the dimensions and paragraphs prepared for measurement.

Organizational Reputation

Organizational reputation is a window of great importance in light of the harsh and difficult global changes and developments. It is important to mention that the reputation of organizations is not a relatively new concept, but it is still of great interest to researchers, managers and stakeholders, as understanding and managing reputation is vital to the success of organizations in a competitive business environment. According to (Carpenter & Krause, 2012: 2), organizational reputation is a set of beliefs about the organization that relate to its capabilities, intentions, history and mission, where beliefs are an integral part of a network of multiple audiences. While (Hendriks, 2016: 7) sees organizational reputation as the overall attractiveness of the organization, or it is the employer's brand or part of the employer's brand. According to (Boistel, 2014: 217), reputation is defined through psychology as a mechanism for assessing the risk of entering into a relationship with an entity (i.e. a person or an institution). (Meynhardt et al, 2019:148) found that it is the level of awareness that the organization has been able to develop for itself. (Al Shuqairat, & Al-Shura, 2021: 29) confirmed that it expresses the evaluation of beneficiaries and customers of the organization's ability to meet their needs, and their impressions of its work and policies. The more positive their opinion is, the more they support and endorse the organization and continue their relationship with it. Soeling et al, (2022:3) defined it as a valuable strategic asset for every business. In light of the above, the researchers believe that organizational reputation is a combination of admiration, trust and respect that is formed in the minds of individuals and the community surrounding the organization, and reflects the comprehensive image of its performance, behaviors, policies and relationships with customers and society. On the other hand, the way of doing business has changed nowadays to a digital form, which has increased the importance of media for individuals and organizations (Berg & Blomqvist, 2019: 18). The value of the organization's reputation has become a center of commercial interest, as it represents an inimitable social resource. In addition, building the organization's reputation is an important part of its value, and reputation is considered one of the strategic assets that can give the organization a competitive advantage and maintain its financial performance. The scale (Sala, 2011: 5) was chosen, which includes four main dimensions (Quality, Attractiveness, Responsibility, Performance) for the research. This scale is characterized by the presence of ready-made paragraphs to measure each dimension.

Methodology

Research Problem

In line with the academic conceptual development and the rapid change witnessed by universities at the local and global levels, and to increase reliance on the concept of green intellectual capital more, this is vital to ensure the continuity of academic activity and achieve excellence in a competitive educational environment (Ali et al., 2021:869). Despite the prominent role of universities in promoting environmental awareness and sustainability, there are challenges facing understanding and adopting the concept of green intellectual capital and its impact on their organizational reputation. These challenges are represented in the weak awareness of some senior leaders of the importance of organizational reputation, as well as the lack of commitment of some universities to environmental and sustainability practices, which exposes them to losing opportunities to enhance their reputation and achieve excellence in the academic arena (Mazzoleni & Nelson, 2005:2). The main problem of the study is the weak cognitive vision of senior leaders in the universities studied regarding the level of importance of the impact of green intellectual capital on the organizational reputation of universities in the holy Karbala, the research sample, and identifying gaps in understanding and applying this concept in the context of academic work. It is expected that applying the results of this study will contribute to improving management strategies and enhancing the organizational reputation of universities, which contributes to strengthening their position in the academic community and society in general.

Research Aims

The aim of the current study is to demonstrate the impact of green intellectual capital on organizational reputation in private universities in Karbala. In addition, we can identify a set of other objectives that the study seeks to achieve, which are as follows:

- 1-** Diagnosing the extent of interest of private universities in Karbala in green intellectual capital and its dimensions (green human capital, green structural capital, green relational capital) and organizational reputation and its dimensions (quality, responsibility, attractiveness, performance).
- 2-** Determining the level of association between green intellectual capital and organizational reputation.
- 3-** Measuring the impact of green intellectual capital on organizational reputation in private universities in Karbala.

Research Importance

Green intellectual capital is one of the important aspects that interest universities and educational institutions at the present time, due to the increasing awareness of the importance of social and environmental responsibility in order to enhance the organizational reputation of organizations. It highlights the importance of private universities adopting green ideas, as this contributes to preserving the environment and building a positive reputation, which enhances the competitive advantage of educational institutions. In addition to clarifying the importance of

examining environmentally friendly activities and providing an idea on how to maintain them, which is closely linked to organizational reputation, as focusing on the sustainability of activities contributes to building a positive reputation for universities and enhancing positive interaction with customers and the local community.

Research Model and its Hypotheses

Figure 1

Research model

H¹: There is a significant correlation between green intellectual capital and organizational reputation in the sample universities.

H²: There is a significant effect of green intellectual capital on organizational reputation in the sample universities.

Research Population and Sample

- 1. Research Community:** Based on the main objective of the study, which is to understand the extent to which green intellectual capital affects organizational reputation, the researchers decided to choose the field of study to be private universities and colleges in Karbala Governorate. These institutions are official institutions that operate under the supervision of the Iraqi Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, and their number is (9) universities and colleges.
- 2. Research Sample:** The research sample included administrative and academic leaders, as the size of the community was (173) directors and the entire community was selected. (131) questionnaires were retrieved, all of which were valid for statistical analysis.

Results

Reliability test for the questionnaire

Verifying the stability of the scale means verifying the possibility of the same results appearing when the same scale is redistributed to the same sample but at two different time points, and the more the stability rate is at (70%) or higher (Joseph et al., 2019: 775). Table (1) shows that the internal consistency of the variables has stability ratios ranging between (0.74-0.94). Through these ratios, it can be proven that the scale is characterized by internal consistency and that the scale is valid for use in exploring variables in the application environment.

Table 1

Reliability of the scale

Variables and Dimensions	Cronbach's alpha	Variables and Dimensions	Cronbach's alpha
Green Human Capital	0.74	Quality	0.80
Green Structural Capital	0.82	Attractiveness	0.84
Green Relational Capital	0.74	Responsibility	0.83
Green Intellectual Capital	0.88	Performance	0.83
		Organizational Reputatio	0.94

Describe and diagnose study metrics and analyze its results

a. Statistical description of green intellectual capital management: After the description of the dimensions, it is clear that all of them are available in high proportions in the application environment, but they differ from each other in terms of the nature and level of availability, which reflects a good agreement for the availability of the variable, supporting the arithmetic mean that reached (3.46), which is a high level of variable availability. This shows that there is a good availability of the green intellectual capital variable in the private colleges in Karbala, the study sample. Table (2) shows a statement of the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, relative importance, level of response, and arrangement of dimensions.

Table 2

Statistical description of green intellectual capital (n=131)

Variable and its dimensions	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Relative importance
Green human capital	3.82	0.742	0.76
Green structural capital	3.35	0.787	0.67
Green relational capital	3.22	0.749	0.64
Green intellectual capital	3.46	0.759	0.69

b. Description and diagnosis of the organizational reputation variable: After the description of the dimensions, it is clear that they are all available at high rates in the application environment, but they differ from each other in terms of the nature and level of availability. At the level of the organizational reputation variable, the dispersion reached a low level of (0.687), which reflects a good agreement for the availability of the variable, supporting the arithmetic mean, which reached (3.74), which is a high level of availability of the variable. This shows that there is a good availability

of the organizational reputation variable in the private colleges in Karbala, the study sample. Table (3) shows a statement of the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, relative importance, level of response, and arrangement of dimensions.

Table 3

Statistical description of the organizational reputation (n=131)

Variable and its dimensions	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Relative importance
Quality	3.70	0.679	0.74
Attractiveness	3.81	0.713	0.76
Responsibility	3.71	0.684	0.74
Performance	3.73	0.674	0.75
Organizational Reputation	3.74	0.687	0.75

Testing the study hypotheses

- a. **Correlation Hypothesis Test:** The content of the correlation hypothesis indicates (there is a direct correlation with a significant moral significance between green intellectual capital and organizational reputation). It was shown through Table (4) the values of the correlation matrix, as it is clear that there is a strong correlation level, as the value of the correlation reached (.623**) and this value is considered statistically acceptable because its significance level reached (Sig=000, < 0.01) in addition to the significance through the two-star mark, which is the highest value of the correlation and is related to the calculated t. It is also clear that the direction of the relationship was direct, as it was shown by the absence of a negative sign above the value. This means that the more the green intellectual capital variable is available in the application environment, the more it is associated with the appearance of the organizational reputation variable within the boundaries of the private colleges in Karbala, the current study sample. The result above supports the acceptance of the hypothesis in the application environment.

Table 4

Correlation coefficients matrix between the research variables

		Green Human Capital	Green Structural Capital	Green Relational Capital	Green Intellectual Capital
Organizational reputation	Pearson Correlation	.528**	.510**	.490**	.623**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000

	N	131	131	131	131
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b. **Effect Hypothesis Test:** It is expressed as (there is a significant effect of green intellectual capital on organizational reputation), as it is clear from the structural model (2) that there is a significant level of influence that is characterized by statistical significance with regard to the employment ability of the independent variable, as it was at an effect level of (B=0.62), which is a significant value based on the Sig value that reached (P-Value=0.01), and its critical ratio reached (9.074), which is a statistically acceptable value because it is higher than the minimum acceptable limit of (1.96), and with regard to the explanatory ability (R²), it is clear that green intellectual capital is able to explain a percentage of (0.39) of the changes that occurred in organizational reputation, while the remaining percentage of changes, estimated at (0.61), is a contribution of other variables and phenomena that were not included in the current study model.

Figure 2

Structural model for testing the effect hypothesis

Table (5) shows the standard and non-standard values of the impact factor, as well as the measurement error and the critical ratio, in light of which and the level of significance, the acceptance of the results becomes clear.

Table 5

Estimates of the impact model between research variables

Variables		S.R.W	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	
Green Intellectual Capital	→	Organizational Reputation	.623	.603	.066	9.074	***

Conclusions

1. Green human capital enhances innovation and creativity in the efficient and sustainable use of resources, which contributes to enhancing economic development and improving the quality of life, and at the same time, contributes to preserving the environment and reducing the negative impacts of economic growth on nature.

2. Organizational reputation is a crucial factor in the success and continuity of organizations in the market. A good reputation reflects integrity, honesty, quality and social responsibility, which ultimately leads to strengthening business relations and attracting investments and human talents.
3. There is a strong statistically significant correlation between green intellectual capital and its dimensions, and organizational reputation. This indicates that the more attention is paid to environmental issues in the application environment, the more it is associated with enhancing the university's position and organizational reputation in general.
4. The existence of a direct effect with a moral significance of green intellectual capital and its dimensions on organizational reputation, indicates an increasing interest on the part of the private universities in the research sample in applying green intellectual capital, as this contributes to attracting the best human competencies and developing their skills by adopting environmental ideas in the work environment, and consequently this interest leads to enhancing the organizational reputation of the university and strengthening its position in the educational community.

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